

THE EXPRESSION OF “GOLD” IS ONE OF THE MOST PROMINENT FEATURE
OF MAGICAL TALES

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Abstract. In this article It is written and given lots of examples with the help of expression the word “gold”. This word is mostly appeared in all the world magic fairy tales. By using this expression or word , the plots and images of magic fairy tales make tales more intriguing and fantastical. it is additionally tried to open features of using the word “ gold” in both English and Uzbek magic tales.

Key words: magic-fantasy, miraculous, a golden castle, a golden boy, a golden cow, a golden fish, a golden tree, a golden quince, a golden purse, a golden egg, a golden spatula.

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ «ЗОЛОТА» — ОДНА ИЗ САМЫХ ЯРКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ
ВОЛШЕБНЫХ СКАЗОК

Аннотация. В данной статье написано и приведено множество примеров с помощью выражения слова «золото». Это слово чаще всего встречается во всех мировых волшебных сказках. С помощью этого выражения или слова сюжеты и образы волшебных сказок делают сказки более интригующими и фантастическими. дополнительно предпринимается попытка раскрыть особенности употребления слова «золото» как в английских, так и в узбекских волшебных сказках.

Ключевые слова: волшебство-фантазия, чудесное, золотой замок, золотой мальчик, золотая корова, золотая рыбка, золотое дерево, золотая айва, золотой кошелек, золотое яйцо, золотая лопаточка.

In magic-fantasy tales, gold, diamond, silver, ruby are often mentioned before the names of some places and things, and their strange, miraculous, unusual, magical properties are indicated. A golden castle, a golden boy, a golden cow, a golden fish, a golden goose, a golden tree, a golden apple, a golden quince, a golden watermelon, a golden flower, a golden purse, a golden egg, a golden chiltor, a golden pot, a golden dress, a golden cup, a golden spatula, golden spoon, golden cradle, diamond sword, golden ball are among them. Of course, these are the products of fiction, because in real life most of them are not found, they are unnatural. Z. Rasulova also touched on this in her dissertation research.¹

It is interesting that the image of gold (silver or diamond) objects can be seen in both English and Uzbek fairy tales. For example, in the British fairy tale "Jack and his Golden Snuff-box" there is an image of a golden snuff-box. In fact, in real life, you can make a snuffbox out of gold. But the fact that three small strange people come out of it and fulfill the wishes of the owner of the snuffbox is based on fiction. which leads to the perception of this object as a magical object.

It seems that in some of them the word gold appears in the title, while in some it is included in the tale. For example, this situation can be observed in the fairy tale "Jack and his Golden Snuff-box". Jack is given the golden snuffbox by the spirit of his father, who orders him to take it out of his pocket and open it only in case of death. A person on Jack's path demands that

¹ Rasulova Z. "Strange items" in Uzbek folk magic tales (specification, genesis and artistry): Philol. Ph.D. diss. autoref. - T., 2012. - p. 24-25.

he build a magnificent lake and have ships with a number of military personnel on it. To do this, Jack uses a golden snuffbox given to him by his father. As soon as he opens the mouth of the box, three little red people come out of it and immediately do what is said.

Jack completes the next two tasks: to build a large castle and to have twelve soldiers standing in the castle with a pillar of gold, using a mysterious tobacco. However, when Jack goes hunting, the horseman, while packing his clothes, takes a golden snuffbox from his pocket. As soon as Ot bogar opened the box, only three people jumped out of the box and said: "Make a wish." Jack the Ripper destroys everything he spawns.

Jack the Mice King and his brothers help the Frogs and the Bird King find the golden snuff box. With her help, Jack is reunited with his wife and adorable son.

Three little red men from a magical golden box fly up the palace with the speed of the wind and bring it back to its original place.

There is a series of English tales associated with the name Jack in which gold is used specifically to exaggerate the properties of magical objects. An example of this is the tale "Jack and the Beanstalk".

In the fairy tale "Jack and the Beanstalk", the hero steals a giant's golden purse, a hen that lays golden eggs, and a golden chiltor. The hen lays golden eggs for them, and the golden chiltor plays beautiful tunes, and the people who listen to it pay them in return.

The magical golden harp (chiltor) musical instrument found in the plot of the fairy tale "Jack and the Beanstalk" plays a tune by itself, even if it is not touched by a human hand. Only a giant controls it. Later, when she is stolen from Jack the Giant, when he knocks, the girl's old clothes change into new ones in the blink of an eye. And thanks to its charming sounds, the mysterious golden goose (or hen) lays golden eggs.

In the fairy tale "Rustamzod and Sherzod" there is an image of a pearl egg, not a golden egg. In a fairy tale, a bird caught by thieves stayed in the old man's house for seven years and laid seven precious eggs. One of these precious eggs is worth more than the wealth of an entire kingdom. When the old man took one of the eggs to the king's palace, the king, who knew its value, gave him a camel full of jewels. The poor old man becomes rich and becomes a big merchant thanks to the pearl eggs.

In the fairy tale "Jack the Grant Killer" ("Jack the Giants' Coup"), the image of the golden trumpet is presented, through which the giant is destroyed. When it is played, all the birds and animals in the enchanted palace will return to their original state. The enchanted palace goes up in smoke and disappears.

The tale of the Uzbek people "Guluyalar and Qalandar bek" talks about the golden castle and emphasizes that everything inside it is made of gold: "Both the flowers blooming in the flower gardens and the fruits on the trees are made of gold... Food is cooked in golden pots... stuffed suck. From the flowers to the dishes here, gold sucks! Golden apples on a golden tree... Golden spatula on the edge of a golden pot...".

In this case, the golden pot, the golden cup, and the golden robe, although they are not claimed to be magical, but by saying that they are made of gold, their mysterious and strange nature is exaggerated. In this tale, the quality of gold is again used to symbolize the nature of the place.

In the English fairy tale "The Golden Arm", the episode "gold" is used to describe a part of the human body in a mysterious way. According to this tale, in ancient times there was a man who

traveled all over the world in search of a wife. He met the young, the old, the rich, the poor, the beautiful and the ugly, but he could not meet the woman of his dreams. And finally he found a young, conscientious and rich woman. This woman's right hand is pure gold. He immediately married her and began to consider himself the luckiest man in the world. The truth is that he loves his wife more because of her golden hands than any other feature. One day his wife died. The husband dressed in black and pretended to be deeply saddened at the funeral, but it was all fake. He got up in the middle of the night, dug up the body and cut off his wife's golden hand. The next night, while the man was sleeping, hiding the golden hand under his pillow, the ghost of his late wife entered the room silently. The ghost went to the side of the bed, pushed the curtain, and looked at her husband angrily. The husband pretended not to be afraid and asked the ghost, "What did he do to your red face, your rose-like lips, and your golden hair?" he asked. And the ghost replied: "Everything has dried up and disappeared." The husband asked, "What happened to your golden hand?" when he said, the ghost said "you took them".

The English fairy tale "The Golden Handle" depicts the turning of objects into gold in the blink of an eye through the motif of transformation. It says that King Midas is a very greedy man who spends his days counting his gold, and though he has a lot of gold, he doesn't think it's enough for him. One day, King Midas saw a half-goat, half-man satyr, gave him some treats and guided him to the right path. The satyr is very pleased with this favor and asks Midas for a wish. And King Midas asks him for gold. On top of that, he says, "May everything I touch turn into gold." Although the satyr tries to tell him that this is not a good idea, Midas does not budge. "to your golden hand?" when he said, the ghost said "you took them". After that, whatever Midas caught turned to gold: golden rock, golden grass, golden leaf, golden ear, golden flower, golden tree branch, golden meat, golden fruit, golden cheese, golden bread. As soon as he sat down to eat, he touched the chair and it turned into gold. As he was about to drink, as soon as he grabbed the cup, it turned into gold in the king's hand. Midas tried to take a sip of water, but immediately a piece of gold stuck in his throat. He held a piece of bread, which immediately turned into gold. Then the king realized his mistake and wept and begged God to free him from this foolish idea. When he cried, his tears shone like small golden marbles. God took pity on the king and directed him to go to the river Pactolus and immerse his body in the water, and be freed from his cursed condition, which he asked for in exchange for a gift. King Midas ran to the river and entered the water to wash his body. At that moment, gold spots were washed from his body into the water. The king came out of the water and felt himself returning to his former state, and ran to his daughter. But the god left a keepsake for King Midas to signify his foolish understanding. Two like donkey's ears grew out of his head.

It is obvious that the expression of gold is always used to describe magical actions and plots in the magic fairy tales. By this way various images and plots could be related to the magic fairy tales that is one of the most intriguing types of fairy tales.

In the fairy tale "The Bear" (Ayiqqolvon) a young man is traveling and sees a beautiful girl sitting in a building crying leaning on a golden chest. A young man sees her and falls in love. When the girl is asked about the name of this country and why she is sitting here alone, she tells that she was the daughter of a king, that a giant escaped here with magic, and that this country is a place of giants. The young man puts the girl in a golden chest, comes to the mouth of the cave, ties the chest to a rope and points to his companions. His accomplices pulled the chest out of the

pit and cut off the rope from which The Bear (Ayiqpolvon) was hanging. In this place, people's desire for gold and a rich country is expressed.

Images of "golden fish" (golden fish) and "golden deer" can also be found in English and Uzbek fairy tales. But the images of "golden watermelon", "golden cradle", "golden chest" were observed only in Uzbek folk tales.

In the fairy tale "Princess of Colchester" ("Princess of Colchester") and "Three heads of the well" (Three heads of the well) three golden heads come out of a magic well and each head asks the girl to wash and comb her hair. The girl agrees, and each head gives her a trait for the good she has done. The first head enhances her beauty, the second gives fragrance to her entire body, and the third helps her become a princess to a prince.

In the same tale, this girl's evil step-sister also follows these paths, but when she comes to the well, she refuses to obey the request of the three heads that come out of it. For this she is punished, the three heads of the well give her punishments such as leprosy, stench and marriage to a simple, extremely poor cobbler.

Andrew Lang's fairy tale "Olloviddin and the Wonderful Lamp" presents the image of strange fruits of gold in a magical garden.

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